

Viscometric studies of aqueous solutions of electrolytes and non-electrolytes

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Viscosities of different solutions containing NaCl, KCl and hexamethylene tetramine (HMTA) in 3.2% (w/v) methanol-water solvent were measured at 20, 25, 30, 35 and 40° from which *B*-coefficient of Jones-Dole equation and $\Delta H_{\eta}^{\#}$ for viscous flow were calculated. *B*-coefficients were found to be positive and *dB/dT* values negative for solutions containing NaCl which expressed the structure-forming nature of NaCl. The usual structure-breaking effect of KCl in aqueous solutions changed in mixed (CH₃OH + H₂O) solvent in the presence of HMTA.

The viscometric behaviour of solutes have been proved to be useful in elucidating the interactions (solute-solute, solute-solvent and solvent-solvent) occurring in aqueous and non-aqueous solutions¹. Binary solutions of electrolytes and non-electrolytes in both aqueous and non-aqueous solvents have been investigated fairly extensively²⁻¹⁰. Surprisingly, very few studies¹¹⁻¹⁶ have been made in ternary mixtures. In our previous studies¹¹ we made investigations on viscosity, thermodynamic properties of flow phenomena, ultrasonic velocity and adiabatic compressibility of aqueous solutions of electrolytes (NaCl and KCl) and polyvinyl alcohol. The present study was undertaken to investigate the effects of mixed solvent on the structure changing properties of electrolytes (NaCl and KCl) in the presence/absence of hexamethylene tetramine (HMTA) in mixed solvent (H₂O + CH₃OH).

Results and discussion

The following four systems have been studied : (i) solvent (CH₃OH + H₂O) + electrolytes (NaCl or KCl), (ii) solvent (CH₃OH + H₂O) + non-electrolyte (HMTA), (iii) solvent (H₂O) + electrolyte (NaCl or KCl) + non-electrolyte (HMTA), (iv) solvent (CH₃OH + H₂O) + electrolyte (NaCl or KCl) + non-electrolyte (HMTA).

The viscosity coefficients obtained are presented in Table 1. The results reveal that except in case (iii) with KCl, the viscosity coefficient always increases with addition of electrolytes or non-electrolyte to the respective solvent.

The relative viscosity coefficients $\eta_{rel} = (\eta/\eta_0)$ were fitted by least square method into Jones-Dole equation

$$\eta_{rel} = 1 + BC + DC^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

to calculate the *B* coefficients for different solutions at different temperatures (Table 2). These were found to be positive and *dB/dT* values negative for solutions containing NaCl which indicated the structure forming nature of the electrolyte. The results also reveal that the usual structure breaking effect of KCl in aqueous solution changes in mixed solvent (CH₃OH + H₂O) in the presence of HMTA.

Thermodynamic quantities of flow phenomena $\Delta G_{\eta}^{\#}$ and $T\Delta S_{\eta}^{\#}$ were calculated by using following relations :

$$\Delta G_{\eta}^{\#} = RT \ln (\eta V/hN_A) = \Delta H_{\eta}^{\#} - T\Delta S_{\eta}^{\#}$$

$$\text{or, } \Delta S_{\eta}^{\#} = (\Delta H_{\eta}^{\#} - \Delta G_{\eta}^{\#})/T$$

Therefore, $\Delta S_{\eta}^{\#} = \Delta H_{\eta}^{\#}/T + R \ln (hN_A/\eta V)$

where *V* represents the volume of hydrodynamic units determined from the density values of respective solutions and considering the number of water molecules involved in the clusters¹⁷, $\Delta G_{\eta}^{\#}$, $\Delta H_{\eta}^{\#}$ and $T\Delta S_{\eta}^{\#}$ represent changes in free energy, enthalpy and entropy respectively during the flow process. $\Delta H_{\eta}^{\#}$ has been taken as equal to activation energy of viscous flow. Experimental results for $\Delta H_{\eta}^{\#}$ are presented in Fig. 1. The results reveal that for the system HMTA and electrolytes, $\Delta H_{\eta}^{\#}$ value increases with the increase of concentration of NaCl but decreases with in-

Table 1. Coefficient of viscosity of different solutions at different temperatures

%CH ₃ OH (w/v)	%HMTA (w/v) water	Electrolyte concentration (mol dm ⁻³)	η (cP)						
			20 ^o	25 ^o	30 ^o	35 ^o	40 ^o		
3.2	-	-	1.0281	0.9174	0.8270	0.7453	0.6672		
		0.1 NaCl	1.0360	0.9231	0.8315	0.7508	0.6726		
		0.2 NaCl	1.0438	0.9289	0.8361	0.7563	0.6780		
		0.3 NaCl	1.0517	0.9346	0.8406	0.7618	0.6833		
		0.4 NaCl	1.0595	0.9403	0.8452	0.7673	0.6887		
		0.5 NaCl	1.0673	0.9461	0.8497	0.7728	0.6941		
		0.6 NaCl	1.0752	0.9518	0.8543	0.7783	0.6995		
		0.1 KCl	1.0302	0.9195	0.8291	0.7490	0.6715		
		0.2 KCl	1.0322	0.9215	0.8312	0.7527	0.6758		
		0.3 KCl	1.0343	0.9236	0.8333	0.7564	0.6802		
		0.4 KCl	1.0363	0.9257	0.8354	0.7601	0.6845		
		0.5 KCl	1.0384	0.9277	0.8375	0.7638	0.6888		
		0.6 KCl	1.0404	0.9298	0.8396	0.7675	0.6931		
		3.2	0.0	-	1.0281	0.9174	0.8270	0.7453	0.6672
			0.5	-	1.0420	0.9211	0.8168	0.7466	0.6737
			1.0	-	1.0561	0.9589	0.8415	0.7600	0.6855
2.0	-		1.0636	0.9490	0.8490	0.7770	0.7005		
-	1.0	-	1.0205	0.9139	0.1890	0.7410	0.6710		
		0.1 NaCl	1.0304	0.9213	0.8237	0.7449	0.6737		
		0.2 NaCl	1.0474	0.9287	0.8284	0.7488	0.6764		
		0.3 NaCl	1.0609	0.9362	0.8331	0.7527	0.6791		
		0.4 NaCl	1.0743	0.9436	0.8378	0.7566	0.6818		
		0.5 NaCl	1.0878	0.9510	0.8425	0.7605	0.6845		
		0.6 NaCl	1.1012	0.9584	0.8473	0.7643	0.6872		
		0.1 KCl	1.0146	0.9090	0.8154	0.7381	0.6695		
		0.2 KCl	1.0086	0.9042	0.8118	0.7352	0.6680		
		0.3 KCl	1.0027	0.8993	0.8082	0.7322	0.6665		
		0.4 KCl	0.9967	0.8945	0.8046	0.7293	0.6659		
		0.5 KCl	0.9908	0.8896	0.8010	0.7264	0.6634		
		0.6 KCl	0.9849	0.8848	0.7974	0.7235	0.6619		
		3.2	1.0	-	1.0561	0.9589	0.8415	0.7603	0.6855
				0.1 NaCl	1.0619	0.9629	0.8439	0.7627	0.6883
				0.2 NaCl	1.0677	0.9670	0.8462	0.7651	0.6911
0.3 NaCl	1.0734			0.9710	0.8486	0.7676	0.6940		
0.4 NaCl	1.0792			0.9750	0.8510	0.7700	0.6968		
0.5 NaCl	1.0850			0.9790	0.8533	0.7724	0.6996		
0.6 NaCl	1.0908			0.9831	0.8557	0.7748	0.7024		
0.1 KCl	1.0657			0.9666	0.8459	0.7649	0.6903		
0.2 KCl	1.0753			0.9743	0.8503	0.7695	0.6952		
0.3 KCl	1.0850			0.9820	0.8547	0.7741	0.7000		
0.4 KCl	1.0946			0.9897	0.8591	0.7787	0.7049		
0.5 KCl	1.1042			0.9974	0.8635	0.7833	0.7097		
0.6 KCl	1.1138			1.0052	0.8679	0.7879	0.7146		

Table 2. Values for B -coefficient of Jones-Dole equation at different temperature

%CH ₃ OH (w/v)	%HMTA (w/v)	Electrolyte concentration (mol/dm ⁻³)	B (mol ⁻¹ dm ³)				
			20 ^o	25 ^o	30 ^o	35 ^o	40 ^o
3.2	0	NaCl	0.0764	0.0625	0.055	0.0739	0.0807
		KCl	0.02	0.0225	0.0253	0.0497	0.0647
0	1.0	NaCl	0.1318	0.0812	0.0575	0.0525	0.0403
		KCl	-0.0582	-0.0531	-0.044	-0.0394	-0.0226
3.2	1.0	NaCl	0.0547	0.042	0.0281	0.0318	0.0412
		KCl	0.0911	0.0804	0.0523	0.0605	0.0707

 Fig. 1. Variation of $\Delta H_{\eta}^{\ddagger}$ with concentration of electrolytes.

crease of concentration of KCl. These suggest the structure intensifying and destroying property of NaCl and KCl respectively. Similar results were obtained by other researchers^{2,3,11,15,18}. The change of $\Delta H_{\eta}^{\ddagger}$ in the case of mixed solvent is very small especially at low concentration of electrolytes. At higher concentration NaCl shows an anomalous behaviour. This indicates that the effect of electrolytes on the structure of mixed solvent becomes complex, possibly due to the H-bond formation between CH₃OH and H₂O.

$\Delta G_{\eta}^{\ddagger}$ values were found to be almost independent of electrolyte concentration. Hence variations of $T\Delta S_{\eta}^{\ddagger}$ values follow similar trends as in the case of $\Delta H_{\eta}^{\ddagger}$ profiles.

Experimental

Stock solutions were prepared by using freshly prepared double-distilled water having specific conductance, $L_s = 1.002 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at room temperature. The reagents used were distilled methanol, NaCl, KCl (all E. Merck) and HMTA (B.D.H.). To avoid the hygroscopic effect, both the electrolytes and HMTA were dried for 24 h in an oven at 110^o and then kept in a desiccator over anhydrous silica gel. For viscosity measurement at different temperatures, an Ostwald (Silberbrand No. 2) viscometer with an ultrathermostat (U10, Poland) was used. Viscosity measure-

ments were calibrated with redistilled water on the basis of the data at different temperature¹⁹.

Conclusion :

It may be concluded that the presence of HMTA alone does not influence the water structure modifying property of NaCl and KCl. But in presence of both CH₃OH and HMTA the above mentioned properties of these electrolytes are changed possibly due to the formation of hydrogen bond between CH₃OH and H₂O.

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